

INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERISTICS OF SPEECH IN CHILDREN WITH AUTISM

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Abstract. This article provides information about intellectual development and the uniqueness of speech in children with autism. The possibilities of intellectual development of children with autism are different: from mental retardation to mild retardation of mental development and the development of a specific manifestation of knowledge processes in a certain field as talent.

Key words: children with autism, intelligence, Asperger's syndrome, school, mental retardation, thinking, speech pathologist, voice.

The specificity of the formation of perceptual processes in children with autism affects the development of intelligence. Some of the children with autism have preserved intelligence and can be trained in the general education program. Among them, the group of children with Asperger's syndrome is significant. In these children, partial ability is clearly manifested by their specific talents in a certain subject, visual arts or activity.

Children of the second group appear to be deficient in intelligence and cognitive processes they suffer from defects. They are a special adaptation close to the general education program they will need education. Preschool due to the lack of such programs from the program designed for the education of children with retarded mental development used, and problems may arise in school education.

The third group of children have intellectual disabilities. They are just mentally retarded education based on the program for children, taking into account the period of adaptation they get.

The quality of thinking operations of children with autism is evaluated, in which the following defects can be distinguished:

- to be able to analyze at a high level, to be able to work with signs and sign formulas simultaneously with the tendency to lose natural connection with objects and separation of secondary characteristics instead of the main characteristics of objects; thinking.

The formation is often accompanied by manipulative thoughts, not the essence the course of the process itself becomes important for the child;

- acceleration of simultaneous registration of stereotype algorithm of mental operations;
- make a mental conclusion based only on criteria that are of personal importance increase.

Uniqueness of speech. Speech defects in children with autism are manifested in insufficient components of communicative processes. Various speech defects are observed. Some children have mutism. Mutism is manifested by the absence of speech, emotional-volitional processes depending on the scope of speech communication and communicative requirements are characterized by the uniqueness of speech. The occurrence of mutism can be considered not as a defect in the formation of speech activity, but as a lack of motivation for speech communication. However, the degree of expression of mutism varies. In complete mutism, the development of the expressive side of speech is expressed very slowly. Individual sounds and combinations of sounds do not manifest themselves in the form of words and phrases, and do not arouse interest in an autistic child. All at the verbal level As a result of their refusal to communicate, they have almost no reserve of passive words it won't happen. Auditory attention is weak and underdeveloped. Examination of such children during the speech aimed at the child, they want to perceive him, imitate him it seems not. Human speech scares an autistic child and it is complete causes emotional discomfort. Speech development in some children there is no land. Such speech defects are often intellectual defects occurs together with.

Children of the second group suffer from partial mutism. The first group. There are preserved possibilities of speech in relation to children. Speak to these children.

Defects of the first level of speech are not fully developed. Can be compared with In some of these children, speech defects are the first and it is manifested in the incomplete development of second-level speech. Autistic the child's speech is expressed autonomously, unlike the speech of a speech therapist, i.e speech is not focused on society and is represented by a combination of separate sounds.

The speech of the third group of children is somewhat formed, approx corresponds to the second and third levels of underdeveloped speech. However, like those in the second group, the speech is without an address, to a specific person, someone it is characterized by the lack of focus of speech on the object. At this stage in the development of speech, an autistic child speaks his "I". faces great difficulties in the field of expression. Self is the word "I".

the difficulties of expressing with the self-understanding of an autistic child, his related to the complexities of personality formation. Autistic child his name does not say and does not use the first person pronoun in his speech. He speaks about himself in the second and third person. His speech is expressed in echolalia, speech stamps, sound combinations, word combinations or separate sentences. Speak up the intonation aspect is unique, the voice is artificial, sometimes distinguished by a falsetto voice stands.

Children of the fourth group are characterized by a certain maturity of the level of speech development. The child can conduct a monologue for a long time. However, conducting a dialogic speech may present its own difficulties. Speech stereotypes, stamps, the slowness of autonomous manifestation are expressed. However, these disadvantages are mitigated by a high level of speech development and partially manifested.

It should be noted that the four separate groups of autistic children with distinct speech disorders are an independent classification, K.S. Lebedinskaya, it does not belong to the autistic dysontogenesis type of O.S. Nikolskaya (1991).

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